

Inhibition of assimilation of Ti with zirconium based thin films

S. Thanka Rajan¹, AnushaThampi VV¹, Takao Hanawa², Peng Chen², B. Subramanian^{1*}

¹CSIR-Central Electrochemical Research Institute, Karaikudi 630 006, India

²Institute of Biomaterials and Bioengineering, Tokyo Medical and Dental University, Tokyo

*Corresponding author e mail: subramanianb3@gmail.com/bsmanian@cecric.res.in

Abstract

A serious problem in implant materials, namely assimilation, whereby calcium phosphate precipitates from body fluids over Ti metal implants might result in bone re-fracture during removal operation of the implanted devices after healing. To control such assimilation, physical vapor deposition of Zr metallic glass (MG) and ZrO₂ on Ti substrates were carried out. The calcium phosphate precipitation was evaluated through immersion test in SBF. The EDAX measurement confirms the absence of Ca on TFMG coated samples with P only was detected and whereas in ZrO₂ films the Ca and P were distributed. In vitro electrochemical corrosion studies indicated that the Zr-based TFMG and ZrO₂ coatings sustained in the stimulated body-fluid, exhibiting superior corrosion resistance with a lower corrosion penetration rate and better electrochemical stability than the bare crystalline titanium substrate. The cytotoxicity studies showed the coatings were graded as zero and non-cytotoxic in nature.

Key words: Amorphous materials, Glass, Surface treatments, Physical vapour deposition, Bioactivity.

Reference

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